

Deep Sequencing Reveals Transient Segregation of T Cell Repertoires in Splenic T Cell Zones during an Immune Response

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Processing of raw sequences

Paired end reads were merged using Paired-End reAd merger (PEAR) version 0.9.11 (Zhang et al., 2014). CDR3 β identification, clonotype clusterization, and correction of sequencing errors such as removal of nonfunctional CDR3 β sequences were performed using the Recover T Cell Receptor pipeline version 0.5.1 (RTCR; Gerritsen et al., 2016). Bowtie version 2.4.4 was used as aligner in the RTCR pipeline (Langmead et al., 2019). Further analyses were performed using R platform for statistical computing.

References

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